

EDEN ISS

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Executive summary

EDEN ISS enables the continual advancement of controlled environment agriculture technologies leading us towards the next step of space exploration and solving pressing issues on earth at the same time.

The report describes the video documentary. It can be viewed under the weblink <https://eden-iss.net/> and <https://eden-iss.net/index.php/2019/04/30/eden-iss-project-video/>

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Acronyms

Acronym	Explanation	Acronym	Explanation
AD	Applicable Document	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
AIAA	American Institute of Aeronautics	IP	Intellectual Property
AS	Aero Sekur S.p.A.	IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
AST	Airbus Defence and Space	ISS	International Space Station
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research	ISLWG	Information Systems Liaison Working Group
BLSS	Bio-regenerative Life Support Systems	ICES	International Conference on Environmental Systems
CEA	Controlled Environment Agriculture	LIT	Limerick Institute of Technology
CNR	National Research Council	LSG	LIQUIFER Systems Group
COSPAR	Committee on Space Research	M#	Month Number
D	Deliverable	PP	Program Participants
DLO	Wageningen University and Research	RD	Reference Document
DLR	German Aerospace Center	R&D	Research & Development
DLR-RY	German Aerospace Center - Institute of Space Systems	SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
EC	European Commission	TAS-I	Thales Alenia Space Italia S.p.A.
EDEN	Evolution and Design of Environmentally-Closed Nutrition-Sources	TBD	To Be Determined
ES	EnginSoft S.p.A.	TPZ	Telespazio S.p.A.
ESA	European Space Agency	UoG	University of Guelph
EU	European Union	WP	Work Package
HS	Heliospectra AB		
IAC	International Astronautical Congress		

1 Introduction

1.1 *Overall Objectives of the EDEN ISS Project*

The EDEN ISS project is interested in promoting its progress in space greenhouse research to the scientific community and to the general public as to ensure continuation of project objectives. The (ultimate) goal of the EDEN ISS project is to further advance controlled environment agriculture technologies for safe food production on-board the International Space Station (ISS) and other planetary outposts.

Through the complete transparency and distribution of project results to researchers and the proactive educational school program that will be designed for students within the EU and Canada, EDEN ISS is interested and committed to creating awareness and excitement regarding the future of human space exploration.

A critical component of future, human space exploration will be the supply of edible food. The development of innovations associated with cultivating food in closed-loop systems is an integral part of a sustainable human presence in space. EDEN ISS will develop an advanced nutrient delivery system, a high-performance LED lighting systems, a bio-detection and decontamination systems and food quality and safety procedures and technologies.

Distribution of the project results to interested parties guarantees an impact to the European economy and enhances the spin-off potential of these validated technologies.

Furthermore, EDEN ISS will study the utilization of the constructed facility for future system implementations (i.e., for other environments/applications), of which results will be made public.

1.2 *Purpose and scope of this document*

This document presents the script of the video documentary with the web-link for viewing. It will be incorporated in the partner's youtube channels and thus distributed widely.

2 Video documentary script

	Text	What to see
<p>Cold opener /Intro</p>	<p>00:34:47 Zabel: Most likely I would go in the morning to the greenhouse, check that all the systems are running and that the plants are healthy.</p> <p>01:04:57 Bamsey: Human spaceflight is definitely a challenge.</p> <p>01:22:03 Stanghellini: you need plants that grow fast, that need little heat, little light and where you don't throw anything away.</p> <p>02:10:59 Imhof: ... a project that take us further into space and makes it possible that we, as a human species will be able to establish human bases on the Moon and Mars.</p> <p>02:58:57 Battistelli: All those conditions push us to have more efficient systems!</p> <p>03:10:39 Schubert: we are bringing together all the different controlled environment agriculture technologies into one forty-foot container. 03:12:33</p> <p>Michelle Bennett 03:46:10: It's all about the taste;</p> <p>02:38:49 Giacomelli:</p> <p>We're talking about human lives, that need food, they need fiber, they need nutrients, to live!</p>	

	<p>EDEN ISS</p> <p>Ground Cultivation Technologies for Safe Food Production in Space</p>	
<p>Motivation / point of departure</p>	<p>02:32:01 Giacomelli: Wherever we go, we gonna need to produce food to feed people. It will be very difficult particularly in the long duration and very distant travel to other planets, to continuously bring food and supplies. The more that can be produced on site, using local resources, the better for the situation. 02:34:29</p>	
	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>EDEN ISS was conceived to test advanced cultivation Technologies for Safe Food Production in Space.</p> <p>Implementation of EDEN ISS as part of a closed loop life support system for long duration space missions is the long-term goal of the project.</p>	

<p>Concept</p>	<p>03:06:40 Schubert: Within our project we trying to validate the key technologies for future habitats on Moon and Mars.</p> <p>Especially in greenhouse systems that will be integrated in those habitats, we want to examine technologies like air management systems, nutrient delivery system, but also light systems and plant health monitoring systems. 03:07:00</p>	
<p>Concept</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>Under the lead of DLR, the German Aerospace Center, EDEN ISS brings together research partners from all over the world, in total 8 countries,</p> <p>from Austria, Canada, Germany, Ireland, Italy, the Netherlands, Sweden and from the U.S.</p> <p>EDEN ISS comprises an interdisciplinary team of space engineers, architects, psychologists, light specialists, and scientists, from the areas of horticulture, food safety, microbiology and environmental research.</p>	
<p>System and implementation</p>	<p>Bamsey: The EDEN ISS greenhouse is really composed of two containers put together: One which is where I'm standing now is the future exploration greenhouse, which - as you can see - is where we're growing plants, the greenhouse aspect. The other container, the other system, is the service section. And that really contains the various technologies that support plant growth.</p>	

		<p>Matthew Bamsey Institute for Space Systems, German Aerospace Center</p>
<p>System and implementation</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>In the service section the International Standard Payload Rack (ISPR) is located.</p> <p>The ISPR is a demonstrator of safe food production in a confined environment under microgravity conditions like on the International Space Station ISS.</p>	
<p>System and implementation</p>	<p>Giorgio Boscheri from Thales Alenia Space 01:14:29: For us the ISS is the first step towards the exploration. So, we want to go on the space station in order to validate key technical and procedural elements in order to be prepared for the next explorations on surface, of Mars, of the asteroids or of the Moon. 01:14:48</p> <p>01:16:10 Boscheri We do provide microbiological control of the environment, that is going to support safe food production on orbit 01:17:35</p> <p>02:56:41 Battistelli: With the EDEN project, we have the possibility to modulate the growing environment of the plant in order to have the best quality in nutritional terms, for the astronauts and for the crew, that will eat those produce.</p> <p>... 02:57:43</p>	<p>Alberto Battistelli Institute of Research on Terrestrial Ecosystems, National Research Council of Italy</p>

	<p>NARRATOR:</p> <p>An important component is the Atmosphere Management System.</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>atmosphere management</i></p>	<p>01:09:00 Bamsey: ... So, the atmospheric management system allows us to control not just temperature, humidity and CO₂, the carbon dioxide, which plants need to grow, but it can also help us remove some of the gases that might accumulate in this box, ... 01:10:05</p>	
	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>The nutrient delivery system provides nutrients and water to the plant roots in the trays.</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>nutrient delivery system</i></p>	<p>04:14:44 Dixon: ... So, there is misting sprayers, there is a whole range of pumps ... using dynamics systems, pumps, to move water into the root zone and take it away and recycle. That's the other thing. everything is recycled, because of course in space there is no such thing as waste. 04:15:27</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>nutrient delivery system</i></p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>The nutrient solution consists of carefully selected ingredients.</p>	
<p>System and implementation</p>	<p>04:17:00 Dixon: It's nitrogen, potassium, phosphor and some eleven other mineral elements ... The difficulty is that plants</p>	

<p><i>nutrient delivery system</i></p>	<p>don't eat the same diet, they don't feed the same diet, of these nutrients all the time. And there are young plants, they have a diet high nitrate but when they get older and start to get into reproductive stages, their diet changes, ... 04:17:48</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>Atmosphere management system</i></p>	<p>Bamsey: we want to optimize how much green, how much biomass we can get from this greenhouse and these other systems control the environment, ... to provide the optimum temperature, humidity, CO2 and light to get as much green stuff out of these boxes. 01:06:54</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>aeroponics</i></p>	<p>NARRATOR <i>A special process of growing plants was used: Aeroponics.</i></p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>aeroponics</i></p>	<p>03:09:44 Schubert: The aeroponics is ... soilless technique,--...where the roots are hanging in the air and are sprayed every ten minutes by a nutrient solution ... 03:10:39</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>LED lighting system</i></p>	<p>NARRATOR <i>The light is one of the most important environmental factors for plants. It is their source of energy.</i></p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>LED lighting system</i></p>	<p>03:58:26 Bochenek: ..., because the plants are immobile, they cannot move around, they get all the information about their surrounding from the light. So, we can use this to manipulate, so they answer to the light, quality's changing, the growth pattern's changing, their morphology, how they look and changing their chemical composition and also flowering</p>	

	<p>pattern. So, we can use it to manipulate, to tell them actually how we want them grow 03:59:57</p>	
<p>System and implementation <i>LED lighting system</i></p>	<p>NARRATOR The lighting system consists of intelligent LED lights designed for closed environments. They are very durable and can withstand harsh conditions and high humidity.</p>	
<p>System and implementation Plant Health Monitoring /Safe Food Production</p>	<p>NARRATOR With the Plant Health Monitoring System, unhealthy and safe-to-eat vegetables can be distinguished.</p>	
<p>System and implementation Safe Food Production</p>	<p>Michelle Bennett 3:49:30: The food is safe to eat. It is grown in a very safe environment where we eliminate a lot of elements such as microbes that would normally be found in plants grown outdoors or in soil. ... We are also able to control the nutrients that it gets, ... So, we are able to minimize the bad molecules within the plant. So, we are able to say definitely yes it safe to grow and safe to eat it.</p>	
<p>System and implementation Plant Health Monitoring /Safe Food Production</p>	<p>05:25:05 Rettberg: ... it's absolutely necessary to do this biomonitoring, when you are really planning to do confined mission like one in a spacecraft. You have to know which microbes are there, if there are pathogens for humans, or in this case for plants, and if they can cause some problems. ... we have to be</p>	

	<p>prepared to identify problems if they occur and to think about measures to avoid them.</p>	
<p>System and implementation Plant Health Monitoring /Safe Food Production</p>	<p>Battistelli: So, we check for the presence of compounds that we want to avoid, by analyzing the plant tissues and also check for the presence of pathogens, of potential pathogens for humans in the vegetables.</p>	
<p>System and implementation Plants</p>	<p>NARRATOR More than 15 different crop species were selected for the greenhouse experiment three tall growing plants like tomato, pepper and cucumber three different types of lettuce radish Swiss Chard a variety of herbs such as basil, chives, parsley, mint, coriander and others and strawberry</p>	
<p>System and implementation Food Production</p>	<p>Cecilia Stanghellini from Wageningen University 01:22:03: And for the leaves, then we have selected also a variety. This for instance have been selected because it's very spicy, it's mustard leaf and it is very spicy. And then we have different colors. How the variety and the freshness have an influence on the psychology. So, it's not only question of resource use efficiency but also must be nice, must be crunchy, must be tasty. 01:24:44</p>	

<p>System and implementation</p> <p>Food Production, taste and texture</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>The EDEN ISS team studied how the variety of vegetables influences the human psychology in terms of taste and texture.</p>	
<p>System and implementation</p> <p>Food Production, taste and texture</p>	<p>Michelle Bennett of University of Limerick 3:51:08: ... I think this is the first time a crew has been trained on how to determine exactly how a crop should taste. Not ok, it tastes nice, but what does the taste mean, because when we look at flavor, flavor is linked back to the anti-oxidants, for example, that are there and other components.</p> <p>If it doesn't taste right, that is also an indication that the nutrition isn't right.</p> <p>So, this is a huge innovation in that the crew themselves become the testers and are able to give us the feedback that we can match to all of the analytical data that we will do when we get the dried plants back.</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>EDEN ISS was tested 400 metres from the German Neumayer-Station III in Antarctica for one full year. The vegetables grown in the greenhouse supplemented the overwintering crew's diet.</p> <p>The testing of the greenhouse under remote conditions is an important step for developing biological life support systems for space missions.</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>01:38:33 Kohlberg: Neumayer-Station is a research platform in Antarctica, German research platform, running year around, with 9 people on the station, situated near the coastal line of Antarctica, but on</p>	

	<p>the moving shelf ice, that is something special. 01:39:03</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>01:43:10 Kohlberg: I think there is a relationship between isolation, this harsh environment, compared to space. The first idea why it goes to Antarctica, to simulate a little bit these nearly same conditions. 01:43:35</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>NARRATOR Project team member Paul Zabel of the DLR joined the Neumayer Station crew for one year to cultivate plants, maintain all subsystems and to conduct research in the greenhouse.</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>Interview Paul Zabel from DLR (XDCAM 3 - Disc 1 - C0085) 00:36:29 Zabel: ... Other plants, like some lettuce that we grow, are most likely harvest every two days, so I would cut away some of the leaves that we then can consume for a dinner. Then there are other plants like radish which don't need much caring. They just grow by themselves and I only have to check that they are doing well. 00:37:16 00:34:47 Zabel: Most of the caring for the plants is done by the systems.... 00:35:25</p>	
<p>Test in Antarctica</p>	<p>NARRATOR All essential stages of plant growth, the functionality and the effectiveness of the subsystems were monitored by Paul Zabel onsite in Antarctica and at the DLR mission control center in Bremen.</p>	

<p>Mission control centre</p>	<p>SCHUBERT</p> <p>... In the mission control room the plants can be observed over thirty-four cameras in each step of their growth. This information gets distributed to EDEN ISS partners all over the world.</p>	
<p>Outcome / results</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>Between February and November 2018, EDEN ISS produced 270kg of fresh vegetables within only 12.5 m² of growth area. This makes around 5kg per week of fresh produce.</p>	
<p>Outcome / results</p>	<p>Bamsey:</p> <p>EDEN ISS is ... laying the groundwork for how we're going to build and have these reliable, biological life support systems in the future. 01:12:31</p>	
<p>Outcome / results</p>	<p>Imhof: All in all, one can say, that, especially the EDEN ISS greenhouse is a unique project, ... to try to pave our way to future exploration of Moon and Mars, deep space and also to return the effects of technology development for this specific closed environment to Earth and for terrestrial applications. 02:07:33</p>	
<p>CLOSING</p>	<p>NARRATOR</p> <p>The EDEN ISS Antarctic facility has been renewed for two more research winters and will produce more fresh vegetables for the overwintering crews at the Neumayer-Station.</p> <p>In this way, more scientific data can successfully be supplied to the world's research community in the coming years.</p>	
<p>Credits</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">German Aerospace Center (DLR), Germany – Project Coordinator</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Institute of Space Systems</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Daniel Schubert</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Paul Zabel</p>	

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2.1 Video access

The video can be accessed through the EDEN ISS website under weblink <https://eden-iss.net/> and <https://eden-iss.net/index.php/2019/04/30/eden-iss-project-video/>

3 Summary

The video documentary was developed to have a short summary video of the project with enticing video footage.

Through interviews with people who worked on the project, the video also shows the diversity of experts contributing to EDEN ISS. The online video documentary explains the goals of the project, how the project came together and how it was tested in Antarctica. It highlights the most important achievements, the way forward and the diverse applications which can be derived from the developed technologies.